

FREQUENCY AND CLINICAL VARIANTS OF BILIARY TRACT IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *At the same time, the proportion of cholelithiasis in children with an upward trend is increasing. In the structure of the pathology of the biliary tract, there is a significant increase in both dysfunctional disorders and diseases of a metabolic-inflammatory nature (1). A certain role in the formation of the pathology of the biliary tract is played by congenital anomalies of the gallbladder and biliary tract. The studies carried out indicate the frequency of lesions of the biliary tract in school-age children. Comparative analysis of the data obtained in a comprehensive study allows differentiating the pathology of the biliary tract, but with a clinical manifestation, and also confirms the informative value of X-ray and ultrasound studies to clarify the diagnosis.*

Keywords: *anomalies, acholoz, dysfunction of the biliary tract, anomaly in the development of the gallbladder and biliary tract, cholecystitis.*

Objective of the study: To assess the informativeness of various diagnostic methods for the differential diagnosis of biliary tract pathology.

Materials and Methods:

In our study, the diagnosis was based on clinical-anamnestic and laboratory data, as well as X-ray and ultrasound examinations. Abdominal organ echographic scanning, particularly of the liver and gallbladder, was performed using standard methods. Oral cholecystography was performed when indicated, allowing for the determination of the gallbladder's shape and function, the diagnosis of anatomical anomalies, and the presence of stones or signs of inflammation. The contents of the duodenum, including sediment and its biochemical analysis, were examined using a microscope.

Besides that, laboratory diagnosis of cholestasis was based on determining alkaline phosphatase, total bilirubin and its fractions, cholesterol, and cytolitic aminotransferases in the blood.

Results: There were examined 89 school-aged children, who were diagnosed with different clinical forms of congenital and acquired biliary tract diseases. Of these, 22 were hospitalized due to suspected inflammatory diseases of the gallbladder, while the remaining 67 were identified during a selective examination.

The study identified the following groups of patients:

Those with dysfunctions of the biliary tract (12-14%);

Those with developmental anomalies of the biliary tract (35-38%);

Those with inflammatory diseases of the biliary tract (chronic cholecystitis, cholecystocholangitis) (42-47%).

Clinical symptoms in each group were characterized by the appearance of signs of abdominal pain syndrome.

Moreover, in children with dysfunctional biliary tract disorders, pain often had a dull character, was moderately pronounced, and brief in duration. In a small number of patients with hypermotor dysfunction of the biliary tract, the pain occasionally manifested as an acute attack. In this group, localized pain in the epigastric region predominated (68%). The pain was typically not

related to food intake but rather to emotional stress caused by unfavorable situations and usually resolved on its own (94%). In some patients, the pain center shifted from the epigastric region to the right hypochondrium (20%). About one-third of patients (38%) experienced pain episodes accompanied by nausea, and rarely vomiting. Long-term symptoms were present only in some patients.

In the group with congenital anomalies in the shape and position of the gallbladder, the abdominal pain syndrome often manifested as an episode (64%) of moderate intensity, was brief, but recurring. A notable feature was the high effectiveness of antispasmodics, which did not show any similarity to dysfunctions of the gallbladder and biliary tract. The zone of palpatory tenderness was identified almost equally, often in both the epigastric region (51%) and the right hypochondrium (49%).

In patients with chronic cholecystitis and cholecystocholangitis, abdominal pain was episodic, moderately intense, brief, and often related to the consumption of large amounts of fatty food. Abdominal pain was frequently accompanied by nausea (65%) and less often by vomiting (25%).

The objective of the study: During the objective examination, the zone of palpatory tenderness was determined in the projection of the gallbladder, as well as in areas of patients without predominant localization in the right hypochondrium, with moderate intensity.

Materials and Methods:

Patients with cholecystitis and cholecystocholangitis showed positive symptoms related to the gallbladder. A clear correlation with food intake was observed ($p < 0.05$). For the dyspeptic syndrome, which was found in more than 80% of the observed patients, no significant differences were identified.

Certainly, attention was drawn to the enlarged liver. Its size varied from 2-2.5 cm to 2.5-3.0 cm below the costal margin. Minimal liver enlargement was mainly identified in patients with biliary tract dysfunctions, while maximum enlargement was found in patients with chronic cholecystocholangitis and anomalies of the gallbladder and biliary tract. In the majority of patients (65%), liver palpation was sensitive, the edge was rounded, the surface smooth, and the consistency soft. In the remaining patients (35%), mostly children suffering from cholecystocholangitis and anomalies of the gallbladder and biliary tract, the liver was not only enlarged but also slightly hardened, accompanied by moderate pain during palpation. In addition to complaints of dyspeptic disorders, these patients also had symptoms indicating an asthenovegetative syndrome.

Definitely, a comparison of the clinical symptoms in different types of biliary tract pathology allowed for the identification of features specific to each form. Thus, patients with cholecystitis and cholecystocholangitis exhibited symptoms of gallbladder dysfunction. Children with biliary tract dysfunctions were characterized by a correlation between the onset of abdominal syndrome and food intake or physical activity. In cases of biliary system anomalies, the use of antispasmodics was highly effective.

General Clinical Blood Tests:

The general clinical blood tests of the children in this group were not specific, with changes characteristic of an inflammatory process found only in 12% of the patients with chronic cholecystitis (cholecystocholangitis). These patients showed accelerated ESR and moderate leukocytosis, as well as signs of body allergies (15%).

Despite the availability of modern diagnostic methods for the biliary tract, the use of the procedure for fractional multi-step closure of the duodenum allows for the evaluation not only of

the gallbladder's mobility and the condition of the sphincter apparatus but also of microscopic changes in the colloidal state of bile.

Results and Discussion:

In cases of biliary tract pathology, if there are no contraindications to the study, fractional duodenal intubation can help to timely detect disorders in biliary function and liver bile function, the motor function of the biliary tract, and determine the key points for treatment and prevention of these conditions (authors).

In our study, the functional state of the biliary system, using duodenal intubation, revealed no deviations in only 5% of children. All the others (95%) had motor disorders. Enzyme studies in bile (ALP) showed varying degrees of changes in enzyme activity across all three groups.

Hypermotor dyskinesia was found in 38% of children, hypomotor dyskinesia 0 in 26%, and confusion in consciousness - in 30%. In 44% of cases, functional disorders were combined with signs of dysfunction. Inflammatory changes in the biliary system were confirmed by the corresponding clinical picture.

Ultrasound Examination Results:

Ultrasound examination of the liver and biliary system revealed an increase in the vertical dimensions of the liver and an increase in its echogenicity in 74 patients (97%) of varying severity. The diagnosis of chronic cholecystitis was confirmed by ultrasound diagnostic criteria such as thickening of the gallbladder wall (54%) and its distension (32%).

The motor function of the gallbladder remained unchanged in only 27% of the children, while all others (73%) showed various forms of impaired tone and contraction rhythm, which determined the nature of the dysfunction. The hypermotor form of dysfunction was found in 35 children (64%), the hypomotor form - in 14 (25%), and the mixed form - in 6 (11%).

It is noteworthy that ultrasound of the gallbladder revealed a parietal sediment in the form of "sand." Ultrasound signs of cholestasis were characterized by the expansion of intrahepatic bile ducts within the liver parenchyma.

Developmental Abnormalities:

In 35 (38%) children, developmental abnormalities of the gallbladder were diagnosed. In our study, the morphological condition of the gallbladder in the observed children was characterized by: S-shaped deformation of the organ in 28.5%, bends in the body of the gallbladder in 42.8%, in the neck section in 20%, and in the neck-bile duct zone in 8.5%. These identified anomalies in gallbladder development were combined with dysfunctions of the biliary tract.

Chronic Cholecystitis:

Chronic cholecystitis is characterized by a prolonged and monotonous course with periodic exacerbations. The leading clinical syndromes include pain, dyspeptic symptoms, and general intoxication syndrome.

Pain Attacks:

Pain attacks occur after physical exertion, stressful situations, dietary mistakes (such as consuming fatty, fried, very sweet foods, eggs, cold and carbonated drinks, etc.), exacerbation of comorbid conditions (such as tonsillitis, pneumonia, etc.), and in some cases, without an apparent reason. The pain is localized in the right hypochondrium, less frequently in the epigastric region, and often radiates to the right shoulder blade, collarbone, shoulder joint, and arm, and more rarely to the left hypochondrium. The pain is dull and lasts for many hours, days, or weeks. Sometimes, sharp, brief, cramp-like pains occur against this background.

Dyspeptic Disorders:

Dyspeptic disorders are usually associated with diet violations and are characterized by sensations of nausea, a feeling of heaviness in the right hypochondrium or epigastric area,

especially after eating; belching; and a bitter taste. In some cases, vomiting occurs with a bitter taste, which does not bring relief. During exacerbations, appetite is reduced, and bowel disorders are sometimes observed, including constipation, diarrhea, alternating between both, as well as bloating, etc.

Mechanism of Dyspeptic Phenomena:

The development of dyspeptic phenomena is associated with impaired bile secretion and changes in the biochemical composition of bile. Bile secretion during the interdigestive period (in the absence of food intake) can lead to biliary reflux into the stomach, nausea, and a bitter taste in the mouth. A decrease in bile acid content in the bile leads to impaired digestion, particularly affecting the hydrolysis and absorption of fats.

Chronic Intoxication Symptoms:

Symptoms of chronic intoxication are present to varying degrees and include headaches, increased fatigue, sleep disturbances, emotional lability, decreased academic performance, and subfebrile temperature. These symptoms were observed in 57 (80%) children.

Atypical Forms of Chronic Cholecystitis:

In atypical forms of chronic cholecystitis (14 children, or 20%), the main signs of the disease—pain and dyspeptic syndromes—are either mildly expressed or absent. In 10 cases (14%), children exhibited significant emotional lability, suffered from episodic headaches, poor sleep, and occasionally had hand tremors and involuntary, obsessive facial muscle movements (tics). In 6 cases (6%), the leading clinical symptoms included persistent subfebrile temperature, polyarthralgia, palpitations, unpleasant sensations and pain in the chest area, shortness of breath, and general malaise.

Differential Diagnosis:

The clinical picture of chronic cholecystitis resembles the symptoms of other gastrointestinal diseases. Therefore, when examining a patient, attention was paid to the presence of pain in the right hypochondrium, as well as positive signs of Murphy, Ortner, Kerr, Hausmann, Vasilenko and Mussi.

Exacerbations:

In 20 (28%) children, rare and brief exacerbations lasting 2-3 days occurred, triggered by dietary mistakes and easily corrected through dietary adjustments.

Chronic Cholecystitis Course:

In the remaining cases (51 children – 80%), chronic cholecystitis (CHC) proceeded with moderate severity, alternating between periods of exacerbation and remission. Exacerbations lasted 2-3 weeks and were characterized by the presence of pain and dyspeptic syndromes, as well as positive signs of gallbladder involvement. These exacerbations were provoked by dietary mistakes and were accompanied by signs of intoxication, pain, dyspeptic symptoms, and changes in biochemical blood markers.

Functional Disorders:

It should be noted that in the context of chronic cholecystitis, children exhibit symptoms of functional disorders, which were confirmed by ultrasound examination.

Role of Anatomical Changes:

As noted in the literature, anatomical changes in the structure of the gallbladder play an important role in the disruption of bile passage. Over time, persistent stasis leads to dystrophic changes in the gallbladder wall, which affects its contractile function. Various types of gallbladder deformation disrupt its normal function, often impairing the motor function of the organ in a hypotonic pattern. Particularly, congenital or acquired pathology in the neck-bile duct zone has a significant impact on the functional state of the gallbladder.

Impact of Compensation Stage:

At the compensation stage, dysfunctional disorders of the gallbladder can be detected through sonographic examination. However, over time, the functional reserves of the gallbladder are depleted, leading to an increase in its volume and atonic changes in the wall. This eventually results in the development of stasis phenomena in the gallbladder, chronic cholecystitis, and the frequent formation of gallstones.

Radiological and Functional Disorders: Radiological-functional disorders in children with biliary diseases revealed impaired contractile function of the gallbladder in 74 patients based on cholecystography results. In 54% of the patients, signs of weakened gallbladder contractility predominated. In 36% of the patients, cholecystography identified anatomical and organic changes in the gallbladder.

Comparison of Ultrasound and Cholecystography Results: While comparing the results of ultrasound (US) and cholecystography, most of the examined children showed complete agreement between the two methods. However, in 11 children (12.3%), this agreement was not observed. In 6 cases, radiological exams did not reveal any abnormalities in the gallbladder, which were identified on ultrasound. The cholecystography results in these cases showed motor dysfunction of the bile ducts, which were misinterpreted as abnormalities on ultrasound. In 6 other children, the motor dysfunction detected by ultrasound was not confirmed by cholecystography, which could be attributed to transient biliary system dysfunctions.

Diagnostic Value of Ultrasound: The comparative study results confirmed that ultrasound is sufficiently informative for diagnosing biliary tract diseases. Nevertheless, in some cases, changes in the shape of the gallbladder detected by ultrasound require radiological confirmation, which is in line with the findings of other researchers.

Excretory Function of the Liver and Biliary Tract: The study of the excretory function of the liver and biliary system revealed a transient nature of the disturbances. This was observed in 44 (49.4%) children. In the clinical picture of transient cholestasis, the predominant signs included subicteric skin and mucous membrane color (24%), liver enlargement by 2-3 cm below the rib cage (39%), recurrent acholic stool (16.4%), and steatorrhea (14.6%).

Laboratory Diagnosis of Cholestasis: Laboratory diagnostics of cholestasis were based on biochemical blood tests, including the determination of alkaline phosphatase, cholesterol, total bilirubin and its fractions, and cytolitic aminotransferases. The biochemical studies revealed elevated alkaline phosphatase levels in 44 (49.4%) children, while hypercholesterolemia was observed in 50% of children. Serum aminotransferase levels remained normal in all observed children.

Conclusion

By summarizing it should be suggested that all studied functional and organic diseases of the gallbladder in school-aged children are accompanied by motor dysfunction. Chronic cholecystitis is more often associated with congenital anomalies of gallbladder development. The research showed that in diagnosing diseases of the biliary tract, all developed examination methods should be used. A rational combination of diagnostic methods used in children allows for the timely identification of both functional disorders and organic diseases of the biliary tract. Moreover, each of these methods has specific advantages in terms of informativeness and specificity. Based on the results of our study, we conclude that ultrasound remains a highly informative method for diagnosing biliary tract pathologies. However, in some cases, the changes in the shape of the gallbladder detected by ultrasound require radiological confirmation, which aligns with the opinions of other authors. An elevated serum bilirubin level was found to be inconsistent and present only in a small number of children (10%). Comparing the clinical

symptoms of patients with inflammatory, dysfunctional disorders, and anomalies of the gallbladder and biliary tract allows for a differentiation of this pathology based on clinical manifestations.

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